

The Effects of Heat Treatment on the Tensile Properties of Camshaft Made of GGG70 Series Spherical Graphite Cast Iron

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Abstract. The aim of this study is to investigate the effects of austempering and induction hardening on the tensile properties of GGG70 ductile cast iron for cam shaft production. For this purpose, cam shafts have been produced by sand mould casting method. For nodulizing process, Fe-Si-Mg alloy has been used and Fe-Si-Ba-Ca-Al alloy has been for inoculation process. The casting has been done between 1420-1440°C and the pouring time was in between 11-13 sec. The casted cam shafts have been austenitized at two different temperatures and time under controlled furnace atmosphere. The austenitized cam shafts have been quenched into the molten salt bath at 320°C temperature and held 90 min and then cooled in air. By this way, austempering heat treatment has been applied. After that, surface hardening process was conducted by induction hardening machine with medium frequency. Microstructures of cam shafts have been examined by optical and mechanical tests (hardness and tensile tests) have been performed. The fracture surfaces of tensile specimens were examined by SEM analysis. Results show that austempering heat treatment increases the tensile strength of cam shaft as-cast condition. Tensile strength of the cam shaft increases with increasing austenitizing temperature, time and induction hardening. The highest tensile strength 1285MPa, has been obtained from the induction hardened cam shaft austenitized at 900°C and 90 min time.

Keywords: Casting, Austempering, Induction Hardening, Tensile Properties, SEM

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1. INTRODUCTION

The production of camshafts used in engines, it is carried out with the casting and machining techniques. Today, camshafts are produced from gray, nodular graphite cast iron, because of many advantages, and also machining of steel [1-2].

Nodular cast iron (ductile iron) is more convenient and easier in terms of production costs compared to production of machining methods. At the same time, it is %10 lighter than steels. Austempered ductile iron (ADI) compared with steel; it has low material and production cost, low density, good process ability and a high vibration damping ability. As a result of the superior properties, it has started being used in many fields and became the subject of this study [3-4].

ADI are commonly used in structural material that should be good wear resistance and tensile strength as camshaft has an important task in engine in automotive industry. These advantages make ADI attractive in industrial applications [5-6].

In ADI, ausferrite (austenite+ferrite) matrix structure is formed in austempering process that differs from bainitic structure being formed in steels. Therefore, it has different mechanical properties. When the literature is reviewed, it is noted that researches on this subject have been going on [7-8].

Spherical graphite cast iron that are hardened by induction are frequently used in structural elements where wear, fatigue and tensile strength should be good, such as camshafts, which are important tasks in motor vehicles in the automotive industry [9-10].

Different structures are formed in ductile graphite cast iron by surface hardening with induction process according to steel materials. Thus, it has different mechanical properties and studies are going about this topic when we see the on literature [11-12].

The aim of this study is to investigate the effects of austempering and induction hardening on microstructure and tensile properties of small sectioned camshaft.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Materials and Methods

Mould sand that will be used in the camshaft casting was prepared. Melting process is conducted in induction furnaces. The chemical composition was analyzed by spectrometer and Atas thermal analysis equipment. Table 1 shows the chemical composition of cast iron used in camshaft production.

Table 1. Chemical analysis of casting camshaft.

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Mg	Cr	Ni	Mo
3,53	2,31	0,19	0,031	0,021	0,049	0,065	0,033	0,02
Cu	Al	Ti	V	Nb	W	Co	Sn	Fe
0,85	0,005	0,01	0,005	0,002	0,003	0,001	0,003	Balance

Nodulizing process was done in the treatment crucible between temperature of 1550-1570°C and Fe-Si-Mg alloy was used for nodulizing treatment. While liquid metal was poured into casting crucible, inoculation process was done by adding Fe-Si-Ba-Ca-Al alloy. Casting process was completed between 11-13 sec and at the temperature of about 1415°C by controlling laser type thermocouple. By this way, camshaft and tensile samples (Y blocks) were casted by sand mold casting method.

Remaining sands on the surface of camshafts and Y blocks has been cleaned by sand blasting device. The runners and risers of camshafts and Y blocks were separated by cutting and their surfaces were ground on CNC machines. Tensile test samples were produced from Y blocks according to ASTM A597 standard (Figure 1).

Figure 1. ASTM A597 standard tensile sample 2D technical drawings

2.2. Heat Treatment

2.2.1. Austempering

In the austempering heat treatments, cabin type furnace is used that works with electrical resistance and can go up to 1100 °C and has atmosphere and temperature control. After the camshafts were austenitized at 800 and 900°C, 60 and 90 minutes, camshafts austempered rapidly in salt bath (%50KNO3+%50NaNO3) at 320°C, 90 minutes duration. After that, camshafts were cooled in air to room temperature.

2.2.2. Surface hardening with induction

When surface hardening heat treatment was conducted with medium frequency induction machine, it was obtained temperature control by thermal cameras for the samples of camshafts. Surface microstructure was changed by induction heating between 4-6s times.

2.3. Metallographic Process

Heat treated camshafts samples were made ready for microstructure investigation by standard metallographic methods (mounting, grinding, polishing) and then etching process was conducted to the

samples by using 2% nital solution. Microstructure of the camshaft was examined under a Nikon MA200 optical microscopy and analyzed by Clemex Vision Lite of image analysis software. % of nodularity, nodule size and number, % volume graphite, ferrite and pearlite were measured. SEM analyses were conducted in order to characterize the fracture surfaces in the tensile test results.

2.4 Mechanical Tests

2.4.1. Hardness Test

Hardness of core sections on camshafts as casted and austempered conditions were measured applying 750kgf load in terms of brinell hardness by Instron Wolpert hardness device. After induction surface hardening process, hardness of each cam surfaces were measured applying 150kgf load from surface in terms of Rockwell hardness by Instron Wolpert hardness device. Hardness test was measured five times from different sections.

2.4.2. Tensile Test

Tensile test machine called ALSA with 20 tons was used for tension test. Tensile strength, yield strength and the amount of % elongation were determined. Tension test were conducted three times and average values of tensile properties were given and then the fracture surfaces of each sample were examined by SEM.

3. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure

Results of image analysis obtained by Clemex Vision Lite program was given in Table 2. As seen in the table; % nodularity, nodule count, nodule size, graphite, ferrite and pearlite volume ratio values are close to that of values in GGG70 cast iron standard. It has shown that the method was implemented in camshaft production was correct and reliable.

Table 2. Microstructural analysis results

Nodularity (%)	Nodule count (mm ²)	Size of nodule (μm)	Graphite Volume (%)	Ferrite volume (%)	Perlite Volume (%)
92	340	28,7	15,61	22,71	61,68

Camshaft microstructure was given in Figure 2, the microstructure is a typical graphite cast iron casting structure. The ductile graphite nodules contain ferrite-converted particles, which are carbonized around the graphite nodules, and a perlitic matrix outside them.

Figure 2. The microstructure of the cast camshaft; a) 100X, b) 200X

After austenitizing process, the microstructures of camshaft samples were given that is austempered at 320°C 90dk. Around the ductile graphite nodules, bainitic ausferrite formed by austempering is seen. Some dark brown-contrasted areas that are resemble sorbitos are also seen. (Figure 3 a-b). The etched microstructure images reveal the austempering effect. The matrix also exhibits a bainitic matrix structure in brown tones with austenite-ferrite grains enaged in light white tones (Figure 3 c-d). The matrix has been transformed into ausferrite structure with the austempering effect, a structure consisting of needle-like

ferrite grains containing precipitates and a mixture of austenite grains brighter in contrast and higher in carbon dissolution (Figure 3 e-h). It is observed that when austenitizing time has increased austenite phase increased in structure also. With increasing austenitizing temperature, it has been obtained a more homogeneous ausferrit. With increasing austenitizing temperature and time, austenite phase was found to be more homogeneous.

Figure 3. Microstructures of austempered camshaft; austenitized at 800°C, 60 min a) 100X, b) 200X; austenitized at 800°C, 90 min c) 100X, d) 200X; austenitized at 900°C, 60 min e) 100X, f) 200X and austenitized at 900°C, 90 min g) 100X, h) 200X

At the Figure 4, the microstructure of the camshaft with austenitized was applied by induction hardened. It is possible to say that the formation of a mixed matrix containing fine graphite nodules as well as fine martensitic and needle ferrites from the etched microstructure images, and this matrix structure is obtained by the effect of induction hardening (Figure 4 a-d). The needle ferrite grains are seen as gray contrasted discs, except this, the matrix is mainly thin martensitic (Figure 4 e-h).

Figure 4. Surface microstructure of austempered and induction hardened camshaft with austenitizing and induction at 800°C, 60 min a) 100X, b) 200X; at 800°C, 90 min c) 100X, d) 200X; at 900°C, 60 min e) 100X, f) 200X and at 900°C, 90 min g) 100X, h) 200X

3.2. Mechanical Tests

3.2.1. Hardness Results

Because the core of camshaft cools more slowly than that of surface, it is softer and measured with Brinell hardness. The hardness tests were applied to the cam cross section that is seen in Figure 5. Depending on heat treatment applied in Figure 5 shows the core and the surface hardness values. The results show that the core of austempered camshaft is 23% harder than that of casted camshaft.

The core hardness of camshaft with austempered + induction hardened is 35% higher than that of casted camshaft. This is due to that cooling rate of core of the austempered camshaft and induction hardened camshaft is higher than that of camshaft with as-cast condition. When their surface hardness values are compared, it is seen that their microstructures were formed differently. With induction hardening heat treatment, martensitic microstructure was obtained on the surface of the camshaft; ausferritic microstructure in austempered camshaft and perlitic-ferritic microstructure in the camshaft with as-cast condition.

Figure 5. The results of hardness camshaft at; a) casting, b) 800°C, 60 min. austenitized, c) 800°C, 60 min. austenitized and inducition hardened, d) 800°C, 90 min. austenitized, e) 800°C, 90 min. austenitized and inducition hardened, f) 900°C, 60 min. austenitized g) 900°C, 60 min. austenitized and inducition hardened, h) 900°C, 90 min. austenitized, k) 900°C, 90 min. austenitized and inducition hardened

3.2.2. Tensile Test Results

Tensile tests were conducted three times for each sample and average values of tensile properties were calculated and submitted. Tensile test results were given in Figure 6. As it can be seen from the result, when austenitizing temperature and time are increased, the tensile and yield strengths increases but % elongation decreases. The highest tensile and yield strength values were obtained from the camshaft with austenitized at 900°C and 90 min This increase in tensile strength and austempering was resulted from an increase in counter resistance to tensile strength according to thin ausferritic structure to perlitic structure.

Figure 6. Tensile test results

SEM analyzes were conducted to characterize the casting fracture surface. Figure 7 shows the fracture surface of tensile test sample as- cast condition. Generally, the fracture surface displays brittle characteristic (a). The fracture surface reflects the fractural characteristics of matrix structure of ferritic-pearlitic.

Facet sections on the fracture surface contain ferritic areas, lamellar looking sections contains pearlitic areas (b). The SEM images of the fracture characteristics examined include the same in the other structures.

Figure 7. The SEM images of samples taken from the surface rupture under casting conditions; a) general view, b) a detail from the middle part, c) high magnification matrix details, d) high magnification details

Fracture surface of the tensile test sample with austenitized at 800°C for 60 minutes are presented in Figure 8. Homogeneous distribution of the graphite and that no segregation tendencies realized in the matrix were revealed. The fracture displays generally a brittle characteristic. Sectional reduction quite low is also observed that the breakage occurs in the material along the cleavage plane of the fracture surface usually at a level of about 1.2% of sample tested (In Figure 8 b, the region inside the red circle and the like). In the fracture surface is often observed that occurrence of the breakage in the material along cleavage planes. However, it is observed that ductile fracture. Beside fracture structure often exhibit fracture particular that is one specific characteristic of austempered cast iron, it also show characteristics of grain boundary fracture.

Figure 8. The images of samples taken from the surface rupture under austempering conditions at 800°C for 60 minutes; a) general view of lower magnifying, b) detail view

Fracture surface of the tensile test sample with austenitized and induction hardened at 800°C for 60 minutes are presented in figure 9 the general view shows that the distribution of graphites is homogeneous in Figure 9a. The section narrowing is at the level of 3.6%. The higher magnification SEM image shows that intragranular fracture occurs in the material (Figure 9b). In this material, surface and inter-center investigations suggested that the surface treatment does not change the general fracture behavior.

Figure 9. The images of samples taken from the surface rupture under austempering and induction hardening conditions at 800°C for 60 minutes; a) general view of lower magnifying, b) detail view

Fracture surface of the tensile test sample with austenitized at 800°C for 90 minutes are shown in Figure 10. General view particularly shows that there is a high nodular graphite density in the central region of the sample. Such heterogeneous in the structure is considered as a disadvantage in terms of mechanical properties. Intergranular fracture was observed on the fracture surface (c).

Cavities are formed by microvoid coalescences mechanism that reflects ductile fracture characteristics in the areas (d). Occurrence of these kind of fracture, it reveals presence of tough section and high ability of plastic deformation in the materials.

Figure 10. Review of samples rupture surface under condition of austempering at 800°C for 90 minutes; a) general view of lower magnifying, b) detail view, c) the detail view of the fracture surface with different secondary phases, d) the plastic deformation zone formed along the sides of the secondary phase

Fracture surface of the tensile test sample with austenitized and induction hardened at 800°C for 90 minutes are presented in Figure 11. The general appearance of the fractured surface shows the graphite segregation in the center (Figure 11a). The section narrowing is around 2.5% and the material is cracked brittle. Advanced fracture intergranular areas were observed on the fracture planes over typical cleavage planes detected on the surfaces of other materials (Figure 11b). But, two different fracture structures are observed on the fracture surface as shown in Figure 11c. In the upper right corner of the SEM image, fracture occurs with brittle fracture in the area marked by the ring, while fracture dissociation in the area within the red square is more ductile. In figure 11d, the higher magnification SEM image of the area marked by the square shows more details of the areas that have higher plastic deformation capability.

Figure 11. The images of samples taken from the surface rupture under austempering and induction hardening conditions at 800°C for 90 minutes; a) general view, b) a detail from the middle part, c) a fracture appearance displaying two different fracture characteristics, d) a detail view of the plastic deformation areas on the periphery of a graphite housing

Figure 12 shows the surface of the tensile test sample with austenitized at 900°C for 60 min. At the high temperature, microvoid coalescence mechanism was observed so ductile fracture in the austenitized sample was seen in the wide areas and graphite distribution was homogeneous, fracture surface was in the mode of ductile fracture (c). The presence of the plastic flow can also be explained by the fact that large areas in the form of pits (d).

Figure 12. The images of samples taken from the surface rupture under austempering conditions at 900°C for 60 minutes; a) view of an internal structure exhibiting two different refractive characteristics, b) like brittle fracture of the detail view

Fracture surface of the tensile test sample with austenitized and induction hardened at 900°C for 60 minutes are presented in Figure 13. The general fracture surface shows no graphite segregation (Figure 13a). The fracture surface contains secondary phase particles as well as areas exhibiting mixed fracture including ductile and brittle fracture (Figure 13 b- d) The analyzes made at different points (regions 1 and

2) in figure 13 d show that the oxide-based particles are MgO based. Oxide based residues are also phase particles that promote fracture such as graphite.

Figure 13. The images of samples taken from the surface rupture under austempering and induction hardening conditions at 900°C for 60 minutes; a) general view, b) a detail from the middle part, c) detail view, d) detail view from near to the surface; oxide particles take place in the ferritic matrix.

Fracture surface of sample with austenitized at 900°C for 90 minutes was presented in Figure 14. The fracture characteristics contains exhibiting mixed rupture separation as fracture surface that is divided in two types; ductile and brittle fracture. Fracture surface contain significant cleavage planes as well as the form of the pits. The refore, the material contained in the mixed fracture in the rupture.

Figure 14. The images of samples taken from the surface rupture under austempering conditions at 900°C for 90 minutes; a) general view of lower magnifying, b) detail view, c) a detail view through sample, d) a detail from a view; fracture surface contains ductile and brittle fracture characteristics

Fracture surface of the tensile test sample with austenitized and induction hardened at 900°C for 90 minutes are presented in Figure 15. In this surface hardened material, the difference in fracture characteristics was found. In low magnification images (Figure 15 a and b), this difference is not very obvious but it occurs at high magnifications (Figure 15 c and d). The brittle fracture occurred in a more similar behavior to the fracture mode of the hardened steels than his ductile fracture.

Figure 15. The images of samples taken from the surface rupture under austempering and induction hardening conditions at 900°C for 90 minutes; a) general view, b) a detail from the middle part, c) detail view, d) detail view that shows the fracture character of the matrix to the surface

It can be concluded that as austenitizing temperature and time are increased, fracture mechanism changes from brittle to ductile type fracture. It is contributed that grain size of austenite increases with austenitizing temperature and time. Amount of ausferrite phase increases with increasing austenitizing temperature and time since increasing of carbon diffusion takes place easily from ferrite phase into austenite phase.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the effects of austempering and austempered+induction hardening heat treatments on the tensile and microstructure of camshaft made of ductile cast iron were investigated and following results were obtained;

1. When microstructure of samples in the camshaft under casting conditions contain graphite nodules and ferritic-pearlitic matrix structure, austempered camshaft samples microstructure contains ausferrite (austenite + ferrite) microstructure. The core of microstructure of camshaft with austempered + induction hardened contains nodule graphite and keep its ausferrite microstructure. The surface of microstructure of that consists of nodule graphite, fine martensite, some untransformed austenite and some needle ferrite.
2. Austempering process applied on GGG70 class nodular cast iron, the core hardness value of nodular cast iron has increased from 261HB to 339HB, surface hardness value from 32.3HRc to 49.2HRc. After induction hardened heat treatment, the core hardness value has increased from 261HB to 365HB, surface hardness value from 32.3HRc to 65.0 HRc.
3. When tensile strength of camshaft with as-cast is compared with that of austempered and induction hardened cast iron, the austempered induction hardened camshafts has 60-65% higher tensile strength than the camshaft with as-cast. The maximum tensile strength was obtained from the camshaft with austenitized and induction hardened at 900°C and 90 min. Similar results were obtained for yield strength. However, the % elongation is decreased by austempering heat treatment.
4. Tensile properties are increased by austenitized and induction hardened temperature and time but decreases in % elongation.
5. Fracture mechanisms were determined by SEM analysis. It was concluded that ductile and brittle fracture modes were observed on all fracture surfaces. When austenitizing temperature and time increases, ductile fracture mode was observed in wide region on the fracture surface. This is due to that amount of ausferritic phase increases in the microstructure. After the surface hardening process, there are more obvious in the brittle fracture areas on the fracture surfaces, and the fracture displays more fracture disintegration in the intergranular.

REFERENCES

- [1] <http://www.obitet.gazi.edu.tr/dokumanlar.html/>
- [2] <http://www.newmancams.com/pdf>
- [3] J. Dodd, *Mod. Casting* 68(5), 60-66 (1978). **DOI:** 10.1007/BF02682710
- [4] Gundlach, R. B. and Janowak, J. F., *Austempered Ductile Iron Combined with Toughness and Ductility*. *Met. Progr.* 128, pp. 19-26. (1995). **DOI:** 10.1007/s00170-011-3469-1
- [5] G.P Faubert, D.J. Moore, and K.B. Rundman, *Heavy Section ADI: Tensile Properties in the As-Cast and Austempered Condition*, *AFS Trans.*, Vol 99, pp. 551-561, (1999)
- [6] Hayrynen KL, Moore DJ, Rundman KB. *Tensile and fatigue properties of relatively pure ADI*. *AFS Transactions*, pp. 93–104, (2002)
- [7] D.J. Moore, T.N. Rouns, K.B. Rundman, *The relationship between microstructure and tensile properties in austempered ductile irons*, *AFS Trans*, pp. 765–774, (2005). **DOI:** S0921-5093(01)009 13-3
- [8] Kilicli V., Erdogan M., *The Nature of the Tensile Fracture in ADI with Dual-Matrix Microstructure*, *Journal of Materials Engineering And Performance*, pp.153-165 (2010). **DOI:** 10.2339/2012.15.1, 43-47
- [9] Mohmmad Hossein N., Saeed K., Mehrdad K., *Nondestructive characterization of induction hardened cast iron, parts 2*, *International Conference on Materials Heat Treatment, ICMH (2011)* **DOI:** 10.5185/am13.ab-2011
- [10] L. Bartosiewicz, A.R. Krause, B. Kovacs, and S.K. Putatunda, *AFS Trans.*, vol. 92, pp.117–43, (1994). **DOI:** 10.1007/BF02682710
- [11] Alabi A., Aluko F., *Production of Austempered Ductile Iron with Optimum Sulphur Level for Effective Mechanical Properties*, *The International Journal Of Engineering And Science (IJES)*, Volume, Issue 12, pp. 67-71, (2013). **doi.org/10.1179/136404610X12693537270091**
- [12] R. Martins, J. Seabra, L. Magalhães, *Ductile Iron (ADI) Gears, Power Loss, Pitting and Micropitting*, *Wear*, Volume 264, Issues 9-10, pp. 838-849 (2008) **doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2017.12.003**